

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

MODERN PARADIGMS OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF KAZAKHSTAN'S INTELLECTUAL POTENTIAL

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Abstract

This article is dedicated to the contemporary state and development of higher education in the Republic of Kazakhstan. It addresses the transformation issues within the framework of strategic planning of the education system, taking into account prospective directions of state policy. Through the study of this theme, based on the enhancement of the intangible sector in the republic, systemic and well-planned approaches to utilizing intellectual potential that contribute to economic growth and the well-being of the population are identified.

Keywords: society, socio-economic development, higher education, science, intellectual potential.

The main regularity of social development at the end of the 20th and beginning of the 21st centuries is the innovative renewal of the global economy, the transition to the so-called "new knowledge-based economy," characterized by the accelerated development of the intangible sphere of economic activity. Modern society is rapidly evolving towards a post-industrial direction, and the transformations taking place are so radical that they can be seen as a shift in the paradigm of economic development.

As is known, the independent republics of the former Soviet Union have been in existence for more than 30 years, and each newly formed state developed depending on its political and socio-economic configuration.

The transition of countries from industrial to post-industrial, information-based societies, and intellectual economies places the intellectual component of human activity at the forefront. The role of science, education, and new technologies - everything related to intellectual potential - is steadily increasing.

In the modern post-industrial society, human capital, which includes the assessment and evaluation of its intellectual potential, is becoming an increasingly strategic resource. The formation of an intellectual nation is one of the strategic goals of development, with a primary focus on building an industrial-innovative economy for the country. Its result is a qualitatively new intellectual nation.

Despite temporary difficulties associated with financial and economic crises, a fundamentally new system for creating public wealth has emerged in the world, based on education, research, and innovation. It is widely known that in economically advanced countries, from 70 to 85 percent of the growth in gross domestic product (GDP) is attributed to new knowledge embodied in technologies, equipment, workforce training, production organization, and other elements [1].

Thus, there is no doubt that in the new conditions, intellectual capital creates the main value for company shareholders, and its most important components - investments in research and development, patents and licenses, trademarks, scientific knowledge, and staff qualifications, internal corporate culture, etc., in other words, objects that do not have a material-physical form, receive market valuation and recognition.

It is important to note that in a knowledge-based economy, the share of labor directly associated with the production of the final product significantly decreases. However, a much larger contribution to its final value is made by labor at the stages of development, prototype creation, market testing, market introduction, and subsequent servicing throughout the product's life cycle. Intellectual work, requiring a high level of knowledge and the intensity of its use, is used in these stages. Moreover, during their implementation, organizations continue to accumulate knowledge, i.e., they self-educate [1, 2].

Currently, the prevailing economic situation in both Kazakhstan and the world necessitates the adoption and implementation of advanced technologies and innovative solutions in production and business processes. Undoubtedly, high results can only be achieved through the development of the country's intellectual potential. The intellectual component of the economy is gaining increasing importance.

The evolution of the national system of higher education is a significant element in the development of the country's intellectual potential.

The concept of "intellectual potential" is understood as the totality of theoretical and practical knowledge of humanity on various aspects of nature and society development, scientific and technical, and cultural achievements. The components of intellectual potential are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Components of intellectual potential are shown

At present, intellectual potential is a relevant economic aspect of societal development. Worldwide, there is a transformation of the process of social production, including the industry of intangible assets as a whole and the industry of scientific research developments in particular.

Intellectual potential encompasses:

A characteristic of a country's or region's intellectual sphere and a source of new knowledge, ideas, information that contribute to increasing the competitiveness of the economy and the living standards of the population.

The ability of a system (state, region, enterprise, organization, etc.) to find unique solutions to achieve significant results in the fields of science, technology, and spirituality.

A measure of the effectiveness of an innovative economy expressed in its capacity to realize the intellectual potential of individuals and society for the purpose of socio-economic development.

The ability of a system (state, region, enterprise, organization, etc.) to find unique solutions to achieve significant results in the fields of science, technology, and spirituality.

The primary function of intellectual potential is the development and implementation of technological and organizational advantages in a competitive environment.

The plan for implementing measures at various levels of regulating the scientific and technical sphere consists of two components:

Implementation tools (development of the country's intellectual potential, establishment of a communication system in the field of science, technology, and innovation, formation of an effective management system, creation of a model for scientific and technical cooperation, expert and public discussions).

Formation principles (analysis, accounting, and systematization; continuity of decisions, programs, tools, mechanisms, and results; consistency and systematization; normative and legal support; risk assessment).

Currently, Kazakhstan is recognized by the global community as a state with a market economy. In a short historical period of gaining independence, Kazakhstan made a breakthrough in its economy through integration into global civilization using progressive new technologies. With significant intellectual potential, Kazakhstan must be concerned with its rational use and

further multiplication. In this context, the role and importance of the modern education system, human capital, which forms the basis of a new level of societal life and constitutes the essential factors and foundation of the country's economic power and national security, are increasing. The higher education system of any country as a social institution bears the primary responsibility for forming the intellectual human resource necessary for the implementation of the innovation development strategy, as the education of society is a prerequisite for the development of all sectors of the economy [3].

Among the key factors of the country's innovative development, intellectual potential occupies an important place. It is a source of new knowledge, ideas, and information contributing to the increase of the economy's competitiveness and the living standards of the population. Therefore, the efficiency of using intellectual potential and creating conditions for its reproduction become a priority direction of the macroeconomic policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan [4].

QS World University Rankings - one of the most influential global university rankings. It was developed in 2004 by Quacquarelli Symonds in collaboration with the British publication Times Higher Education. Each year, QS evaluates approximately 3,000 universities, selecting the best among them.

In the QS World University Rankings, only universities that offer all levels of education - bachelor's, master's, and doctoral degrees - are included. Additionally, the university must cover at least two out of five knowledge areas: humanities and arts; engineering and technical sciences; natural sciences; medicine and life sciences; social sciences and management.

QS World University Ranking. As it turns out, the list includes 21 universities from nine cities in Kazakhstan. A total of 2,963 universities from around the world participated in the survey, with only 1,499 universities from 104 countries making it into the ranking.

Among the universities in Kazakhstan, Al-Farabi Kazakh National University tops the global ranking, occupying the 230th position on the list. It is followed by L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University at 355th place and Satbayev University at 481st place.

South Kazakhstan State University named after M. Auezov made it to the ranking at positions 611-620. Kazakh National Agrarian Research University is placed at 641-650, Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University at 681-690, Hoca Ahmet Yesevi International Kazakh-Turkish University at 781-790.

The list continues with Almaty Technological University (ATU) and Karaganda Technical University at positions 801-850, Karaganda State University named after E.A. Buketov at 851-900, D. Serikbayev East Kazakhstan State Technical University and Asfendiyarov Kazakh National Medical University at 901-950, KIMEP University at 951-1000, Kazakh University of International Relations and World Languages named after Abai Khan and Kazakh-British Technical University at 1001-1200 [5].

Modern socio-economic requirements emphasize the role of innovative processes in managing the higher education system of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Given the transformation of its content, methods, forms, and organization, by creating new technological support for the educational process, the education system has the opportunity to become an effective resource for societal development, including its innovative component (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Modern processes of transformation of the higher education system in Kazakhstan until 2025

Kazakhstan's Higher Education is celebrating its 95th anniversary in 2023. Currently, 609,000 people are enrolled in 118 higher and (or) postgraduate education institutions in the country, including 228,000 under the state educational order. The gross coverage of higher education (percentage of those receiving higher education among the total population of the five-year age group following the completion of secondary school) stands at 62%, which is significantly

lower than many countries (Russia 82%, South Korea 94%, Ireland 78%, Belarus 81%).

According to national statistics, there were 21,617 scientific workers in the field of science in 2021, of whom 17,092 were research specialists. 35% of them hold academic or scientific degrees (1,652 doctors of science, 3,838 candidates of science, 1,952 PhDs, and 55 in specialized fields) [6].

Figure 3. Dynamics of the number of scientists in Kazakhstan in the context of gender and age indicator, %

In terms of age groups: 35% of scientists are under 35 years old; 42% are between 35 and 54 years old; and 23% are over 55 years old. Women make up 54%, while men make up 46% (Figure 3).

The state policy of the Republic aimed at supporting promising directions in the development of education includes the following components:

- Selection and support of priorities,
- Preservation of the strategic core of innovative potential,
- Promotion of market relations development.

There is a trend of increasing state support for the sector of intellectual development of the economy while simultaneously enhancing the role of its innovative development. The development of educational infrastructure is also a key goal of the government, as it is expected to have a multiplier effect on the economy [7].

In recent years, support for young scientists has grown, and measures have been taken to attract them to the field of science. More than a thousand young scientists and researchers are working on 631 research projects with a total budget of 19.1 billion tenge. According to the competition documentation requirements, in each project funded by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the share of young scientists and researchers should be at least 40%.

The transformation of the content of educational services and the role of the research component in it has influenced the understanding of innovations in universities. Therefore, innovations in Kazakhstan's universities should not be limited to pedagogical innovations alone. Innovation in Kazakhstan's universities can be considered the implementation of relevant reforms in the higher education system, bringing novelties to all types of activities in higher education institutions.

Thus, the balanced development of the higher education system in the Republic of Kazakhstan implies

the existence of conditions in higher education institutions for the implementation of opportunities and the ability of higher education management to carry out innovative changes.

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